

Could an equity index fund emerge as a new form of money?

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Abstract

The financial innovations of recent decades have led to the emergence of equity index funds, which are becoming increasingly popular among investors. From an economic point of view, these funds have remarkable monetary qualities.

In his treaty about monetary systems (2016), Professor Pascal Salin [suggests](#), for the currencies of the future, a possible return to guarantees of convertibility in terms of goods:

“It is even conceivable that these guarantees of convertibility could again be given in terms of gold, but all sorts of other solutions are conceivable: a “basket” of commodities or raw materials, but also a “basket” of stocks, for example those included in the CAC40 or the Dow Jones, or an even more abstract index.”

We will hence examine this proposition with an attempt to demonstrate that a basket of stocks, and more specifically an equity fund based on a global index, would display all the qualities needed to act as a new money. Such a fund would potentially offer stronger monetary qualities than gold and crypto assets.

The emergence of an asset as money

So, what does the theory say about the emergence of an asset as money? And in a free money market, why would this validate the selection of an equity index fund?

The most widely spread theory within the Austrian school of economics was [built](#) by Carl Menger, the founder of the same school. This theory is based on the observation of assets, and in particular of their degree of liquidity. During a spontaneous selection process, the most liquid asset would emerge as the common medium of exchange, i.e., as money, in order to overcome the limits of barter.

It would be easy to conclude that stocks, which are relatively liquid assets, thus have solid monetary qualities. However, there is a flaw in this theory: the concept of liquidity *presupposes* the existence of a monetary system, which makes it inadequate to explain the emergence of a currency from a state of barter, or after the fall of a monetary system. This theory is therefore more akin to an ex post definition of the characteristics of money, which is always the most liquid asset. About the concept of liquidity, Kristoffer Moustén Hansen [explains](#):

““Liquidity” after all simply means that an asset is more certainly realizable at short notice without loss [...] – i.e., that one expects to be able to sell it for money at short notice at its expected market price. In other words, liquidity is a purely derivative concept and depends on the existence of a primary money [...]”

So, is there another theory that can be used to explain the emergence of a new currency?

“An alternative thesis regarding the origin of money as a medium of exchange regards money primarily as a means for accumulation of wealth”, [write](#) Taghizadegan, Stöferle, Valek et Blasnik.

In an established monetary system, the main function of money is undoubtedly to serve as the common medium of exchange. But when it comes to the *emergence* of a new asset as money, the *prior accumulation* of this asset is probably decisive.

Menger implicitly supports this thesis in his [writings](#): in the early stages of economic development, he writes, the accumulation of skins among hunting tribes naturally led to their monetization; among nomads, cattle, the chief item of wealth, was used as a means of payment; and at a more advanced stage of economic development, the accumulation of precious metals preceded their monetization.

Menger [summarizes](#) this thesis quite explicitly in his article *Geld* :

“Hoarding [...] by its nature is older than the appearance of the exchange of goods and money.”

Indeed, it seems logical that from a barter economy, or following the collapse of a currency, only a previously accumulated asset would serve as a new money. The same is true from an established monetary system: when an asset is the usual means for hoarding at the expense of money, it becomes an object particularly suited to future exchanges, and it is natural that it should also become the new unit of account, and then the common medium of exchange.

The monetary qualities of equity index funds

From this point of view, *to conceive the money of the future, we first need to look at the assets composing people's savings*. The most common assets, apart from money itself and claims on money (term deposits and bonds), include rental properties, works of art, precious metals... and *stocks*.

Secondly, we need to focus on assets possessing the monetary qualities usually described in economics treaties, such as homogeneity, divisibility, and durability. In this way, we can eliminate rental property and works of art, which are neither homogeneous nor divisible... unless you own a portion of them in the form of stocks. That leaves us with precious metals and stocks as potential media of exchange.

These days, in the United States and in Europe, stocks represent a [significant](#) share of people's savings. Some people are even probably unaware that they own stocks via their life insurance policies and retirement savings plans. In addition, through the financial innovations of recent decades, new equity-diversified funds have emerged, that track major indices such as the S&P500 or the MSCI World. Most of these “index funds” offer relatively low fees and are now listed on stock markets in the form of “ETFs”. This makes them very accessible, which probably explains their [growing](#) popularity.

From a monetary point of view, an equity fund is easy to divide into homogeneous units, and its storage cost is relatively low, probably cheaper than that of gold, since it is composed of dematerialized property titles. An index fund also has a notable quality: *durability*. Indeed, within such a fund, stocks move in and out over time, according to one or several criteria. The ultimate perpetual fund could for instance be composed of a fixed number of international stocks, selected according to a single criterion, such as the companies' capitalizations. Such a selection would be comparable to that of the MSCI All Country World Index or of the FTSE All World Index.

It must be acknowledged that other assets, such as gold and crypto assets, also have the monetary attributes mentioned above. To conceive the selection of an asset as money, it is therefore necessary to come back to the question of hoarding.

An asset is a good means for hoarding when, over time, it preserves a purchasing power in relation to other assets. To ensure this, according to price theory, the relative scarcity of the supply for this asset is only one side of the coin: the existence of a *relatively strong and persistent demand* is the other crucial element. And since demand depends on the subjective preferences of individuals, it is always speculative to consider any given object as a good means for hoarding. However, we can at least look at the sources of the demand for these different assets, i.e., the variety of services that they render, before we speculate on the permanence of the demand.

In the case of gold, the demand has been sustained for millennia by jewelry and hoarding. But while gold accessories are still very popular today, particularly in Asia, it is conceivable that one day this metal will fall out of favor. The fragility of the demand is much worse for crypto assets: to date, they have no recognized use other than exchange or hoarding.

In contrast, the owner of an equity fund is entitled to the control of a highly diversified spectrum of assets and economic activities. Stocks also have an important feature, which supports their demand for hoarding: they potentially offer a *yield*. It is striking to note how an equity fund, in a monetary form, would display the same features as one of the earliest historical currencies, namely cattle: these assets, commonly representing the wealth of individuals, also embody full economic activities, and they offer potential returns.

About the historical evolution of money, Carl Menger [concludes](#):

“Thus money presents itself to us, in its special locally and temporally different forms, not as the result of an agreement, legislation compulsion, or mere chance, but as the natural product of differences in the economic situation of different peoples at the same time, or of the same people in different periods of their history.”

After cattle, associated with farming, and metals, linked to the rise of the industry, it is therefore conceivable that a new money would emerge in the future, based on an equity fund, which represents the contemporary economy in all its diversity. To begin with, it is conceivable, for example, that a major retail company might one day sell an equity fund to its customers, before setting the price of its services in terms of that same fund.

Thousands of years after livestock, will common stocks become the new money?

Appendix: details about the links and references

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<https://mises.org/library/principles-economics>

>> About the degrees of marketability of goods and the origin of money: chap. 7 and 8.

>> About animal skins becoming money: p. 270.

>> About cattle becoming money: p. 263.

>> About the historical evolution of money: p. 271.

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>> About precious metals becoming money: p. 48.

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<https://mises.org/library/collected-works-carl-menger-german-four-volumes>

>> About the accumulation of assets: p. 55, my translation. Also cited by Taghizadegan *et al.* (2015, 82).

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>> About the origin of money: p. 81.

>> About the accumulation of assets: p. 82.